

Classification of proposals

(each proposal into 2 subjects)

Level of Organization	Subject Area
Molecular	Genomics/proteomics
Molecular	Molecular evolution
Organism	Development
Organism	Physiology/Functional Morphology
Organism	Behavior/Neurobiology
Organism	Medicine
Population	Evolutionary Ecology/Population Biology
Population	Evolutionary Genetics
Population	Phylogeography/Speciation
Population	Conservation
Phylogeny	Comparative Biology
Phylogeny	Systematics/Phylogenetics
Phylogeny	Paleontology
Education	Education

Science awards (yrs 1-4)

<u>Primary or secondary subject:</u>	<u>All awards</u>
Genomics/Proteomics	10
Molecular evolution	13
Development	8
Physiology/Functional Morphology	12
Behavior/Neurobiology	7
Medicine	3
Evolutionary Ecology/Population Biology	21
Evolutionary Genetics	19
Phylogeography/Speciation	10
Conservation	2
Comparative Biology	20
Systematics/Phylogenetics	15
Paleontology	10
Education	6

Cross-disciplinarity of Science awards (yrs 1-4)

	Molecular	Organism	Population	Phylogeny
Molecular	4	5	8	8
Organism		2	9	10
Population			10	10
Phylogeny				9

Science Awards: Integrating Science, Informatics & Education

	Science	Informatics	Education
Science	55	12	3
Informatics		6	0
Education			3

